

Conference Abstract

Larval morphology of *Osmoderma cristinae* Sparacio, 1994 (Coleoptera: Cetoniidae)

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Abstract

Osmoderma cristinae Sparacio, 1994 is an endemic beetle of Sicily (Coleoptera: Cetoniidae). It is a saproxylic species and has a very important role in the forest ecosystems. It is included in multiple national and international "Red Lists" as Endangered species (Audisio et al. 2014, Cáliz et al. 2018). At the larval stages *O. cristinae* participates in the degradation of "dead wood" in old trees, in their cavities, and in downed logs. In this work, the larval morphology of *O. cristinae* is described.

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